

Effective amount of N fertilizer for direct seeding on wet surface of reclaimed saline soil in Korea

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The demand for changing cultural methods from machine transplanting to direct seeding is a current trend in Korea. We identified the appropriate amount of N fertilizer for direct seeding on a wet surface of reclaimed saline soil in Korea.

The experiment was conducted at the Gyehwa substation of the Honam National Agricultural Experiment Station during 1996-97 using a randomized complete block design with three replications on saline soil that contained 0.2-0.4% NaCl in soil solution. Four N levels were tested with a control of 210 kg N ha⁻¹ as standard fertilization for machine transplanting. The results showed that seedling establishment increased slightly up to 180 kg N ha⁻¹ but decreased at 210 kg N ha⁻¹ in direct seeding. Culm length is higher in direct seeding with 210 kg N ha⁻¹. Field lodging in the maturing stage is more serious in direct seeding than in transplanting, as noted by the score of 5 out of 9 under visual assessment (Table 1).

Panicle number and spikelet number per unit area increased significantly at above 180 kg N ha⁻¹ compared with machine transplanting at 210 kg N ha⁻¹ as a control. The percentage of ripened grains and 1,000-grain weight were higher for machine transplanting than direct seeding at the same amount of N. Milled rice yield showed no significant differences between direct seeding and machine transplanting at the same amount of N (Table 2). As a result, we found that the appropriate N level for direct seeding in reclaimed saline soil was 180 kg ha⁻¹. This amount will best prevent field lodging and save on fertilizer and labor costs. ■

Table 1. General characteristics of rice as influenced by N fertilizer under wet seeding in reclaimed saline soil, Gyehwa, Korea, 1996-97.

Cultural method	N amount (kg ha ⁻¹)	Seedling establishment (no. m ⁻²)	Heading date	Culm length (cm)	Field lodging ^a
Direct seeding	100	100	12 Aug	79	0
	150	110	12 Aug	81	1
	180	115	13 Aug	83	3
	210	99	14 Aug	84	5
Machine transplanting (standard)	210	—	16 Aug	80	3

^aOn a scale of 0-9, where 0 = none, 1 = low, and 9 = high.

Table 2. Yield components and yield according to amount of N fertilizer under wet seeding in reclaimed saline soil, Gyehwa, Korea, 1996-97^a.

Cultural method	N amount (kg ha ⁻¹)	Panicles (no. m ⁻²)	Spikelets (no. m ⁻²) × 10 ³	Ripened grain (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Milled rice yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Yield index
Direct seeding	120	375 b	26.6 c	85.1 b	24.6 a	4.6 b	91
	150	381 b	28.8 b	85.3 b	24.5 a	4.7 b	93
	180	397 a	30.9 a	84.1 bc	24.9 a	4.8 a	96
	210	401 a	31.9 a	83.2 c	23.8 b	4.7 ab	94
Machine transplanting (standard)	210	346 c	27.2 bc	89.7 a	25.3 a	5.1 a	100

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

Identifying optimum seeding time for direct seeding on a wet field surface in reclaimed saline soil in Korea

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Rice cultivation in Korea is changing from machine transplanting to direct seeding to save on labor costs and to increase profits. We therefore identified the appropriate seeding time for direct seeding on a wet field surface in

reclaimed saline soil in the southern part of Korea.

The experiment was conducted at the Gyehwa substation of the Honam National Agricultural Experiment Station during 1996-97 using a split-plot design with three replications in a saline soil that contained 0.2-0.4% NaCl in soil solution. Three varieties were used to represent each maturing type: Shinunbongbyeo (early maturing), Gancheokbyeo (mid-maturing), and Gyehwabyeo (late maturing). The results showed that for Shinunbong-

Table 1. Seedling establishment (no. m²) according to seeding times on a wet field surface in reclaimed saline soil^a, Gyehwa, Korea, 1996-97.

Seeding time	Shinunbongbyeo	Gancheokbyeo	Gyehwabyeo
10 May	103 a	104 a	108 a
20 May	97 a	109 a	107 a
30 May	92 a	98 a	93 a
10 Jun	89 a	79 b	76 b

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.